

Fast, Low-resource, Accurate, Robust, and Effectual Medical Image Analysis: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Fast, Low-resource, Accurate, Robust, and Effectual Medical Image Analysis

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

FLARE

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Medical imaging plays a pivotal role in modern healthcare, enabling accurate diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment planning for a wide range of diseases. Despite significant advances in deep learning-based methods for medical image analysis, several challenges remain in creating general models that are fast, resource-efficient, accurate, and robust across diverse clinical and computational tasks. Addressing these challenges is vital to improving healthcare globally, especially in resource-constrained settings. During the past four years, we have organized four challenges to address these limitations with community efforts.

- FLARE 2021: four abdominal organs segmentation in CT scans; Data: 511 CT scans
- FLARE 2022: 13 abdominal organs segmentation in CT scans; Data: 2300 CT scans
- FLARE 2023: 13 abdominal organs and pan-cancer segmentation in CT scans; Data: 4500 CT scans
- FLARE 2024: pan-cancer segmentation, abdominal CT organ segmentation on laptops, and unsupervised domain adaptation for abdominal organ segmentation in MRI Scans; Data: 10,000+ CT scans, 4000+ MRI scans.

The top algorithms can simultaneously segment 13 organs and various abdominal lesions within 10 seconds for a 3D CT scan with over 1,000,000 voxels, which substantially improved the segmentation accuracy, efficiency, and generalization ability. In FLARE 2025, we aim to address critical clinical needs and technical challenges in disease diagnosis and the development of foundational and multimodal AI systems that can generalize across medical imaging modalities. Specifically, the challenge is designed to advance the state of the art in medical image analysis through six innovative subtasks:

1. Pan-cancer segmentation: develop robust algorithms capable of segmenting lesions across multiple disease types in CT scans

2. Abdominal CT Organ Segmentation on Laptop: develop resource-efficient methods that can perform accurate segmentation on computationally limited devices, promoting accessibility in low-resource settings.
3. Unsupervised Domain Adaptation for Abdominal Organ Segmentation in MRI and PET Scans: develop adaptation methods from CT to unseen modalities (i.e., MRI and PET) without extensive labeled data, fostering generalizability and scalability.
4. Foundation Model for 3D CT and MRI: develop versatile, pre-trained models that can serve as a basis for a variety of downstream diagnosis tasks in 3D medical imaging.
5. Multimodal Model for Medical Image Parsing: develop generalist vision-language models that can handle classification, detection, counting, measuring, and regression tasks for various image modalities.
6. Agentic System for Medical Image Analysis: develop large language model-based systems capable of interacting with users to call medical image analysis tools to solve various medical image analysis tasks.

The envisioned impact of this challenge includes driving innovation in resource-efficient, generalizable, and multimodal AI systems, setting new benchmarks for performance and applicability in medical image analysis. From a biomedical perspective, successful methodologies will directly impact patient care by enabling accurate and reliable imaging solutions accessible to diverse healthcare settings, bridging gaps in diagnostic capacity between resource-rich and resource-limited environments.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Efficiency, Pan-cancer Segmentation, Foundation Models

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

FLARE challenge focuses on addressing critical limitations in current AI-driven medical imaging systems. The novelty lies in its multi-faceted approach to advancing these aspects across a range of innovative and clinically relevant tasks.

- Task 1-Pan-Cancer Segmentation: Unlike traditional lesion segmentation tasks, this subtask aims to create models that generalize across multiple cancer types. This addresses the heterogeneity in CT scans, pushing the boundaries of current segmentation models that are often disease-specific.
- Task 2-Abdominal CT Organ Segmentation on Laptop: This task emphasizes computational efficiency by requiring models to run effectively on laptops. This approach promotes democratization of AI technologies, enabling access to advanced image analysis tools in resource-constrained settings without reliance on high-performance computing infrastructure.
- Task 3-Unsupervised Domain Adaptation for Abdominal Organ Segmentation in MRI and PET Scans: By focusing on domain adaptation without labeled target domain data, this task targets a pressing real-world challenge: the need for robust generalization across different imaging devices and settings. The emphasis on unsupervised techniques is both technically challenging and clinically significant.

- Task 4-Foundation Model for 3D CT and MRI: Inspired by the success of foundational models in natural language processing and computer vision, this task aims to establish a similar paradigm in medical imaging. Developing pre-trained, general-purpose models for 3D CT and MRI analysis is a novel endeavor with the potential to transform workflows across a variety of medical applications.
- Task 5-Multimodal Model for Medical Image Parsing: The integration of multimodal images into a unified analysis framework represents a frontier in medical imaging. This task challenges participants to develop vision-language models capable of handling different modalities and tasks, addressing a significant gap in current AI methods that typically focus on single modalities.
- Task 6-Agentic System for Medical Image Analysis: This task introduces a new paradigm of interactive, adaptive, and user-centric AI systems in healthcare, pioneering integration of LLMs with medical image analysis tools. Traditional medical image analysis tools are largely standalone systems requiring domain expertise to operate effectively. This task disrupts this norm by creating agentic systems that transform static tools into dynamic, conversational assistants. These systems not only interpret user instructions in natural language but also adaptively determine the optimal sequence of actions to solve complex medical imaging problems.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

N/A

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

This challenge has six subtasks, which need a longer time for top teams to present their solutions.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We had 37 and 35 successful docker submissions in FLARE 2023 and 2024, respectively. We expect 50-100 docker submissions in FLARE 2025 because the tasks are expanded.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings. The top three teams in each task will be invited to write a challenge summary paper.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We plan to organize an on-site challenge and only need basic equipment: projectors, computers, monitors, loud speakers, and microphones

TASK 1: Pan-cancer segmentation in CT scans

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Deep learning has emerged as the predominant method for cancer segmentation in CT scans. However, most existing models are designed and trained for specific cancer types, limiting their generalizability and scalability. With the rising prevalence of various cancers and the increasing demand for personalized medicine, there is a critical need for a universally applicable, resource-efficient, and highly accurate pan-cancer segmentation method.

In MICCAL FLARE 2024, we introduced the first pan-cancer segmentation challenge on whole-body CT scans, pushing the boundaries of cancer segmentation research. The winning solution achieved DSC and NSD scores of 0.43 and 0.46, respectively, indicating significant room for improvement. This has inspired us to continue organizing this challenge to drive further advancements in pan-cancer segmentation.

Our challenge task has three main features:

- Task: whole-body cancer segmentation (automatic and promptable), across diverse cancer types.
- Dataset: 15,600 CT scans (15,000/100/500 for training/validation/testing), covering whole-body cancer types
- Evaluation Metrics: segmentation accuracy (DSC, NSD) and segmentation efficiency (runtime and GPU consumption)

Compared to FLARE 2024, we have increased additional 5000 annotated CT scans for model development, aiming to empower participants to build more robust and accurate models, ultimately advancing the state of the art in pan-cancer segmentation.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Pan-cancer, Lesion, Segmentation, Universal Model

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Song Gu (Nanjing Anke Medical Technology Co., Ltd.)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2024 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic, Semi automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Launch challenge registration and release training and validation data.

15 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Release validation dataset and open validation submission.

15 August 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Deadline for the testing submission.

1 September 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Invite top teams to prepare presentations and participate in the MICCAI 2025 Satellite Event.

23/27 September 2025: Announce final results at MICCAI.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains and global data contributors with license permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Intervention follow up, Intervention planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with over 15 cancer types, such as lung cancer, liver cancer, kidney cancer, pancreas cancer, and so on, which were curated from 50+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The image data will be released as compressed Nifti1Image objects stored in .nii.gz files. These files will include an affine matrix and header defining the rotation, origin, and spacing of each image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can segment various lesions in CT scans.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Hardware requirements,Runtime,Robustness,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

[2] Heller N, et al. The kits19 challenge data: 300 kidney tumor cases with clinical context, ct semantic segmentations, and surgical outcomes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00445 (2019).

[3] Clark K, et al. The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): maintaining and operating a public information repository. Journal of Digital Imaging 26, no. 6 (2013)

[4] Ma J, et al. Abdomenct-1k: Is abdominal organ segmentation a solved problem. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (2021).

[5] Grossberg A, et al. Imaging and Clinical Data Archive for Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma Patients Treated with Radiotherapy. Scientific Data 5:180173 (2018)

[6] Fedorov A, et al. DICOM reencoding of volumetrically annotated Lung Imaging Database Consortium (LIDC) nodules. Medical Physics (2020)

[7] Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. The Lancet Digital Health 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

[8] Ma. J, et al. Automatic organ and pan-cancer segmentation in abdomen ct: the flare 2023 challenge. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2408.12534

[9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services

Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil

Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI

BioPartners, CA
Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA
Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA
Cleveland Clinic
Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA
Hebrew University of Jerusalem
International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan
IRCAD Institute Strasbourg
Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA
Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich
M Health Fairview
M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX
Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN
Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)
National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD
National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD
Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montreal
Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen
Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY
Sheba Medical Center
St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ
Tel Aviv University
The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)
University of California, San Francisco, CA
University of Chicago
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC
University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA
University of Sheffield
University of Southern California
Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO
Cancer Center West China Hospital
Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT scan associated with/without the segmentation mask.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases is 15,600. There are 15,000/100/500 cases for training, validation, and testing, respectively. Compared to the dataset in FLARE 2024, we increase 5000 annotated lesions.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission and evaluation.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the testing cases are unseen and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

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b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The lesion annotations were generated by semi-automatic segmentation with MedSAM and manual correction. Annotators and radiologists were asked to use 3D Slicer software to annotate the measurable lesions based on RECIST.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Segmentation accuracy metrics: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Normalized Surface Distance (NSD).

Segmentation efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics are complementary. Specifically, DSC and NSD are used to measure the region error and boundary error, respectively.

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams). Specifically, missing results will get a zero value for DSC, NSD and the equivalent worst value for running time, and area under GPU memory-time curve.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2024 and FLARE 2021-2024.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will verify the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

TASK 2: Abdominal CT Organ Segmentation on Laptop

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The past MICCAI FLARE challenges have demonstrated the possibility to achieve a good trade-off between segmentation accuracy and efficiency. For example, in the FLARE 2022 challenge, the winning solution can accurately segment a large CT scan, comprising over 1,000,000 voxels, in less than 10 seconds, all while consuming less than 2GB of GPU memory. Despite these advancements, a critical consideration arises in low-resource environments, such as laptops or hospital imaging edge devices, where GPU resources may not be available.

This leads us to the question: Is it feasible to adapt state-of-the-art abdominal segmentation models for deployment in non-GPU environments without compromising on segmentation accuracy? To explore this possibility, we set up this task to benchmark **CPU-based abdominal segmentation algorithms.** This task was introduced in FLARE 2024, which was the first challenge for benchmarking CPU-based segmentation models for 3D CT scans. Although some participants have achieved better segmentation accuracy or fast inference speed during FLARE 2024, none of them beat the FLARE 2022 winning solution in terms of the overall rank. The results have motivated us to continue organizing this challenge to drive further advancements in efficient segmentation models. Moreover, a parallel coreset track was introduced to benchmark data-efficient solutions.

In an effort to ensure comparability with the winning solution of the FLARE 2022&2024 challenge, this task will utilize the same dataset, which includes 2050 cases for model training. The old validation set and testing set are merged as a new validation set with 250 cases. We provide a new testing set with 300 cases for this challenge. The evaluation metrics include DSC, NSD, and running time, providing a holistic assessment of the algorithm performance.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Efficient segmentation, Abdominal organs, Laptop, Fast

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Cheng Ge (Ocean University of China)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

Life cycle type

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Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2024 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

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- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
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All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

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a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

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a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
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- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Intervention follow up, Intervention planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

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- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

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We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

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The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with various abdominal diseases, which were curated from 30+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The image data will be released as compressed Nifti1Image objects stored in .nii.gz files. These files will include an affine matrix and header defining the rotation, origin, and spacing of each image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can segment the liver, spleen, pancreas, right kidney, left kidney, stomach, gallbladder, esophagus, aorta, inferior vena cava, right adrenal gland, left adrenal gland, and duodenum from CT scans without using GPU.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Runtime, Hardware requirements

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

[2] Heller N, et al. The kits19 challenge data: 300 kidney tumor cases with clinical context, ct semantic segmentations, and surgical outcomes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00445 (2019).

[3] Clark K, et al. The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): maintaining and operating a public information repository. Journal of Digital Imaging 26, no. 6 (2013)

[4] Ma J, et al. Abdomenct-1k: Is abdominal organ segmentation a solved problem. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (2021).

[5] Grossberg A, et al. Imaging and Clinical Data Archive for Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma Patients Treated with Radiotherapy. Scientific Data 5:180173 (2018)

[6] Fedorov A, et al. DICOM reencoding of volumetrically annotated Lung Imaging Database Consortium (LIDC) nodules. Medical Physics (2020)

[7] Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. The Lancet Digital Health 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

[8] Ma. J, et al. Automatic organ and pan-cancer segmentation in abdomen ct: the flare 2023 challenge. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2408.12534

[9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services
Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil
Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI
BioPartners, CA
Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA
Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA
Cleveland Clinic
Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA
Hebrew University of Jerusalem
International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan
IRCAD Institute Strasbourg
Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA
Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich
M Health Fairview
M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX
Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN
Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)
National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD
National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD
Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montral
Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen
Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY
Sheba Medical Center
St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ
Tel Aviv University
The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)
University of California, San Francisco, CA
University of Chicago
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC
University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA
University of Sheffield
University of Southern California
Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO
Cancer Center West China Hospital
Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT scan associated with/without the segmentation mask.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases is 2600. There are 2050/250/300 cases for training, validation, and testing, respectively.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission and evaluation.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the testing cases are unseen and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

7

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotation pipeline is the same as previous FLARE organ segmentation challenge

Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. *The Lancet Digital Health* 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

Specifically, we applied a hierarchical annotation pipeline that consisted of three stages to ensure accuracy and consistency throughout the annotation process. In the first stage, an annotation consensus was formulated by a senior radiologist, an oncologist, and a surgeon based on radiation therapy oncology group consensus (RTOG) panel guideline and Netter's anatomical atlas. Specifically, the liver contour should include all hepatic parenchyma and all liver lesions. The hepatic vessels inside the liver also need to be covered. If the vessels are located outside the liver (i.e., the entrance of portal hepatitis) based on the coronal view, they should be excluded from the liver contour. The kidney contour should include the renal parenchyma while excluding adjacent structures such as blood vessels and surrounding fat.

The spleen contour should include all splenic parenchyma and any splenic lesions. It should exclude adjacent structures such as the splenic vessels (arteries and veins), particularly those located outside the spleen. The pancreatic contour should encompass all pancreatic parenchyma including the head, body, and tail, as well as any pancreatic lesions. Exocrine, endocrine components, and the pancreatic duct need to be included, but the surrounding vessels and fat should be excluded. The aortic contour should include the entire lumen of the aorta, from the aortic root to the bifurcation. The aortic wall (including the aortic calcification) should also be included. The inferior vena cava contour should include the entire lumen and cover the walls. The adrenal gland contour should include the entire adrenal gland, both cortex and medulla, and any adrenal lesions. The gallbladder contour should encompass the entire gallbladder wall, including the body, fundus, and neck, as well as any gallstones or polyps. The cystic duct and the surrounding liver parenchyma should be excluded. The esophagus contour should include the entire esophageal wall, while adjacent structures such as the trachea, aorta, and surrounding fat and muscle should be excluded. The stomach contour should encompass the entire stomach wall including the fundus, body, antrum, and pylorus, as well as any gastric lesions. The duodenum contour should include the entire duodenal wall from the duodenal bulb to the ligament of Treitz, along with any duodenal lesions. It should exclude surrounding structures such as the head of the pancreas, common bile duct, and surrounding vasculature.

Before the annotation process, all annotators were required to learn and follow the annotation consensus.

The second stage of our annotation pipeline involved a human-in-the-loop approach aimed at enhancing annotation throughput. To facilitate this process, we utilized five 3D U-Net models trained via 5-fold cross-validation on existing abdomen CT datasets. Leveraging the predictions generated by these models, junior annotators performed manual refinements with the assistance of MedSAM on 100 randomly selected predictions, which were then checked and revised by senior radiologists. This process was iterated seven times until all the images were labeled by one of the junior annotators and further refined by the senior radiologists. In the third and final stage, we aimed to identify potential annotation errors. We trained a new set of U-Net models using five-fold cross-validation, with special attention given to images exhibiting low Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) scores (<0.75), which were then double-checked by the senior radiologists.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Segmentation accuracy metrics: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Normalized Surface Distance (NSD).

Segmentation efficiency metrics: Runtime.

GPU metrics are not used in this task because the algorithms are evaluated on GPU workstation.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics are complementary. Specifically, DSC and NSD are used to measure the region error and boundary error, respectively.

Running time is used to measure the model efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams). Specifically, missing results will get a zero value for DSC, NSD and the equivalent worst value for running time.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2024 and FLARE 2021-2024.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will verify the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

TASK 3: Unsupervised Domain Adaptation for Abdominal Organ Segmentation in MRI and PET Scans

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Abdominal organ segmentation in CT scans has gained substantial attention over the past decade, leading to the establishment of numerous benchmarks and challenges, such as MICCAI BTCV, MICCAI MSD, MICCAI LiTS, MICCAI KiTS, MICCAI FLARE, and MICCAI AMOS. However, other commonly used imaging modalities, such as abdominal MRI and PET, remain relatively underexplored. A major bottleneck is the scarcity of annotated scans in the community. For instance, the MICCAI AMOS challenge training set includes only 40 labeled MRI scans.

In contrast, a wealth of annotated abdominal CT scans or high-quality pseudo-labeled data (achieving approximately 90% DSC) is readily available. This disparity raises an important question: **How can we build effective abdominal organ segmentation models for MRI and PET using abundant CT annotations?**

To address this, we organized the **unsupervised cross-modality domain adaptation task** for abdominal organ segmentation in MRI scans in FLARE 2024. The winning solution achieved impressive DSC and NSD scores of 0.73 and 0.77, respectively, demonstrating the potential of cross-modality adaptation. These promising results have motivated us to further expand the task in FLARE 2025 to include PET scans, marking another significant step in advancing segmentation research across imaging modalities. Key features:

- Task: the first unsupervised multi-modality domain adaptation for abdominal organ segmentation in MRI and PET scans
- Dataset: a diverse and large-scale abdominal CT dataset (2050), MRI dataset (5098), and PET dataset (1300)
- Evaluation Metrics: segmentation accuracy (DSC, NSD) and segmentation efficiency (running time and GPU consumption)

Compared to FLARE 2024, this year's challenge introduces the PET modality with 1,000 scans, offering participants a new avenue for developing and evaluating models capable of robust multi-modality adaptation.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Unsupervised Domain Adaptation, Multi-Modality Segmentation, Abdominal MRI and PET, Cross-Modality Learning, Segmentation Efficiency

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Yao Zhang (Lenovo Artificial Intelligence Laboratory)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2024 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

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All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

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- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
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23/27 September 2025: Announce final results at MICCAI.

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Our dataset was curated from public domains and global data contributors with license permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

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Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

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Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Intervention follow up, Intervention planning

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State the task category(ies)

Examples:

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- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with various abdominal diseases, which were curated from 30+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, and Positron Emission Tomography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The image data will be released as compressed Nifti1 Image objects stored in .nii.gz files. These files will include an affine matrix and header defining the rotation, origin, and spacing of each image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can segment the liver, spleen, pancreas, right kidney, left kidney, stomach, gallbladder, esophagus, aorta, inferior vena cava, right adrenal gland, left adrenal gland, and duodenum from MRI and PET scans.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Hardware requirements,Runtime

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

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c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services

Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil

Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI

BioPartners, CA

Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA

Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA

Cleveland Clinic

Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA

Hebrew University of Jerusalem

International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan

IRCAD Institute Strasbourg

Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA

Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich

M Health Fairview

M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX

Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN

Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)

National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD

National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD

Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montral

Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen

Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY

Sheba Medical Center

St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ

Tel Aviv University

The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)

University of California, San Francisco, CA

University of Chicago

University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC

University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA

University of Sheffield

University of Southern California

Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO

Cancer Center West China Hospital

Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT/MRI/PET scan associated with/without the segmentation mask.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training set: CT: 2050; MRI: 4688; PET: 1000

Validation set: MRI: 110; PET: 100

Testing set: MRI: 300; PET: 200

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission and evaluation.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the testing cases are unseen and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

7

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotation pipeline is the same as previous FLARE organ segmentation challenge

Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. *The Lancet Digital Health* 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

Specifically, we applied a hierarchical annotation pipeline that consisted of three stages to ensure accuracy and consistency throughout the annotation process. In the first stage, an annotation consensus was formulated by a senior radiologist, an oncologist, and a surgeon based on radiation therapy oncology group consensus (RTOG) panel guideline and Netter's anatomical atlas. Specifically, the liver contour should include all hepatic parenchyma and all liver lesions. The hepatic vessels inside the liver also need to be covered. If the vessels are located outside the liver (i.e., the entrance of portal hepatitis) based on the coronal view, they should be excluded from the liver contour. The kidney contour should include the renal parenchyma while excluding adjacent structures such as blood vessels and surrounding fat.

The spleen contour should include all splenic parenchyma and any splenic lesions. It should exclude adjacent structures such as the splenic vessels (arteries and veins), particularly those located outside the spleen. The pancreatic contour should encompass all pancreatic parenchyma including the head, body, and tail, as well as any pancreatic lesions. Exocrine, endocrine components, and the pancreatic duct need to be included, but the surrounding vessels and fat should be excluded. The aortic contour should include the entire lumen of the aorta, from the aortic root to the bifurcation. The aortic wall (including the aortic calcification) should also be included. The inferior vena cava contour should include the entire lumen and cover the walls. The adrenal gland contour should include the entire adrenal gland, both cortex and medulla, and any adrenal lesions. The gallbladder contour should encompass the entire gallbladder wall, including the body, fundus, and neck, as well as any gallstones or polyps. The cystic duct and the surrounding liver parenchyma should be excluded. The esophagus contour should include the entire esophageal wall, while adjacent structures such as the trachea, aorta, and surrounding fat and muscle should be excluded. The stomach contour should encompass the entire stomach wall including the fundus, body, antrum, and pylorus, as well as any gastric lesions. The duodenum contour should include the entire duodenal wall from the duodenal bulb to the ligament of Treitz, along with any duodenal lesions. It should exclude surrounding structures such as the head of the pancreas, common bile duct, and surrounding vasculature.

Before the annotation process, all annotators were required to learn and follow the annotation consensus.

The second stage of our annotation pipeline involved a human-in-the-loop approach aimed at enhancing annotation throughput. To facilitate this process, we utilized five 3D U-Net models trained via 5-fold

cross-validation on existing abdomen CT datasets. Leveraging the predictions generated by these models, junior annotators performed manual refinements with the assistance of MedSAM on 100 randomly selected predictions, which were then checked and revised by senior radiologists. This process was iterated seven times until all the images were labeled by one of the junior annotators and further refined by the senior radiologists. In the third and final stage, we aimed to identify potential annotation errors. We trained a new set of U-Net models using five-fold cross-validation, with special attention given to images exhibiting low Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) scores (<0.75), which were then double-checked by the senior radiologists.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Segmentation accuracy metrics: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Normalized Surface Distance (NSD).

Segmentation efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics are complementary. Specifically, DSC and NSD are used to measure the region error and boundary error, respectively.

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams). Specifically, missing results will get a zero value for DSC, NSD and the equivalent worst value for running time, and area under GPU memory-time curve.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2024 and FLARE 2021-2024.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will verify the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

TASK 4: Foundation Model for 3D CT and MRI scans

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Foundation models—large, pre-trained models capable of generalizing across multiple tasks—have revolutionized fields like natural language processing and computer vision. However, their potential remains largely unexplored in the realm of 3D medical imaging. This task seeks to bridge this gap by encouraging the development of versatile, high-performing models that can serve as unified backbones for diverse diagnostic tasks using CT and MRI scans. This task challenges participants to design and train foundation models capable of processing volumetric CT and MRI data while excelling in a variety of downstream diagnostic tasks with minimal task-specific fine-tuning.

Participants will have access to a comprehensive dataset comprising 10,000 CT scans and 10,000 MRI scans for developing modality-specific foundation models. The models must be trained using self-supervised learning techniques, leveraging the vast dataset to learn robust representations. Additionally, 100 labeled cases per modality with disease annotations will be provided for fine-tuning or linear probing. To rigorously assess the models, a hidden testing set will be used to evaluate their generalization ability across unseen data.

Key Features:

- Task: The first challenge designed to benchmark foundation models for CT and MRI.
- Dataset: A large-scale dataset with 10,000+ CT scans and 10,000+ MRI scans for self-supervised pre-training and downstream fine-tuning.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Foundation model, Transfer Learning, Linear Probe, Embedding

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Sumin Kim (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2024 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Launch challenge registration and release training and validation data.

15 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Release validation dataset and open validation submission.

15 August 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Deadline for the testing submission.

1 September 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Invite top teams to prepare presentations and participate in the MICCAI 2025 Satellite Event.

23/27 September 2025: Announce final results at MICCAI.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains and global data contributors with license permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification,Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with various diseases, which were curated from 50+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography and Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The image data will be released as compressed Nifti1Image objects stored in .nii.gz files. These files will include an affine matrix and header defining the rotation, origin, and spacing of each image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can classify various diseases in CT and MRI scans.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Hardware requirements,Runtime

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

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[9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services

Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil

Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI

BioPartners, CA
Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA
Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA
Cleveland Clinic
Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA
Hebrew University of Jerusalem
International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan
IRCAD Institute Strasbourg
Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA
Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich
M Health Fairview
M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX
Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN
Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)
National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD
National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD
Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montreal
Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen
Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY
Sheba Medical Center
St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ
Tel Aviv University
The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)
University of California, San Francisco, CA
University of Chicago
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC
University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA
University of Sheffield
University of Southern California
Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO
Cancer Center West China Hospital
Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT/MR scan associated with/without the segmentation mask.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training set: CT: 10,000 unlabeled scans + 100 labeled scans; MRI: 10,000 unlabeled scans + 100 labeled scans;

Validation set: CT: 100; MRI: 100

Testing set: CT: 500, MRI: 500

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission and evaluation.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the testing cases are unseen and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

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b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The disease labels are obtained from radiology reports or pathological examinations.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Accuracy metrics: AUROC and balanced accuracy

Efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The accuracy metrics are selected based on the recommendation in Metrics Reloaded.

Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nat Methods 21, 195–212 (2024).

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2024 and FLARE 2021-2024.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will verify the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

TASK 5: Multimodal Model for Medical Image Parsing

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Multimodal models represent a transformative approach to unify various tasks via general token representation. This capability is particularly valuable in medical imaging, where a wide range of imaging modalities and tasks are integral to clinical workflows. This task requires to develop multimodal models that can handle five typical tasks (classification, detection, counting, measuring, and regression) across nine image modalities (CT, MRI, PET, ultrasound, X-ray, OCT, pathology, microscopy, and endoscopy). In particular, participants should training a multimodal model capable of generalizing across the following tasks:

- Classification: Identifying specific diseases, anatomical structures, or conditions
- Detection: Locating and labeling regions of interest, such as lesions or abnormalities.
- Counting: Enumerating specific entities, such as cells, glands, and lesions.
- Measuring: Quantifying dimensions, volumes, or other clinical attributes from images.
- Regression: Predicting continuous variables, such as bone age, and disease progression

Key Features

- Task Diversity: This is the first multimodal challenge, which require models perform five distinct tasks, showcasing their versatility and ability to adapt to varied clinical needs.
- Modality Integration: Models must harmonize the unique characteristics and data distributions of nine imaging modalities, ensuring consistent performance across them.
- Efficiency and Scalability: Solutions should be computationally efficient, demonstrating practical scalability for deployment in real-world clinical and research settings.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multimodal Learning, Medical Image Parsing, Unified Token Representation, Cross-Modality Integration

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Mohammed Baharoon (Harvard University)

Yaqi Wang (Communication University of Zhejiang)

Jieyun Bai (Jinan University/The University of Auckland)

Yuankai Huo (Vanderbilt University)

Meng Lou (The University of Hong Kong)

Yuanfeng Ji (Stanford)

Yutong Xie (MBZUAI)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2024 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)

- the release date(s) of the results

1 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Launch challenge registration and release training and validation data.

15 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Release validation dataset and open validation submission.

15 August 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Deadline for the testing submission.

1 September 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Invite top teams to prepare presentations and participate in the MICCAI 2025 Satellite Event.

23/27 September 2025: Announce final results at MICCAI.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains and global data contributors with license permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection,Localization,Prediction,Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with various diseases, which were curated from 50+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Positron Emission Tomography, ultrasound, X-ray, Optical Coherence Tomography, endoscopy, fundus, and microscopy images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The 2D and 3D image data will be released as compressed Nifti1Image and JPEG formats, respectively. These Nifti files will include an affine matrix and header defining the rotation, origin, and spacing of each image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can conduct classification, detection, counting, measurement, and regression tasks.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Hardware requirements,Runtime

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

[2] Heller N, et al. The kits19 challenge data: 300 kidney tumor cases with clinical context, ct semantic segmentations, and surgical outcomes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00445 (2019).

[3] Clark K, et al. The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): maintaining and operating a public information repository. Journal of Digital Imaging 26, no. 6 (2013)

[4] Ma J, et al. Abdomenct-1k: Is abdominal organ segmentation a solved problem. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (2021).

[5] Grossberg A, et al. Imaging and Clinical Data Archive for Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma Patients Treated with Radiotherapy. Scientific Data 5:180173 (2018)

[6] Fedorov A, et al. DICOM reencoding of volumetrically annotated Lung Imaging Database Consortium (LIDC) nodules. Medical Physics (2020)

[7] Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. The Lancet Digital Health 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

[8] Ma. J, et al. Automatic organ and pan-cancer segmentation in abdomen ct: the flare 2023 challenge. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2408.12534

[9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services

Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil

Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI

BioPartners, CA

Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA

Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA

Cleveland Clinic

Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA

Hebrew University of Jerusalem

International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan

IRCAD Institute Strasbourg

Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA

Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich

M Health Fairview

M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX

Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN

Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)

National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD

National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD

Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montral

Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen

Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY

Sheba Medical Center

St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ

Tel Aviv University

The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)

University of California, San Francisco, CA

University of Chicago

University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC

University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA

University of Sheffield

University of Southern California

Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO

Cancer Center West China Hospital

Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT/MR/PET scan or an ultrasound, X-ray, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), endoscopy, fundus, and microscopy image.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training set (lesion detection and measurement in various disease): CT: 10,000; MRI (lesion detection and measurement in various abdominal cancer types): 10,000; Microscopy: 1000; Ultrasound: 700; X-ray (permanent teeth detection in panoramic X-ray images): 1000; OCT: 100; Pathology (glomeruli counting and detection in various chronic kidney diseases): 1000; Endoscopy Images (polyp detection): 1000

Validation set: CT: 100; MRI: 100; Microscopy: 100; Ultrasound: 100; X-ray: 100; OCT: 10; Pathology: 100; Endoscopy Images: 50

Testing set: CT: 300, MRI: 300; Microscopy: 400; Ultrasound: 200; X-ray: 200; OCT: 50; Pathology: 200; Endoscopy Images: 100

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission and evaluation.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the testing cases are unseen and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

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b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The disease labels are obtained from radiology reports or pathological examinations. Other detection and counting labels are obtained by manual annotations.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifITy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Accuracy metrics:

Classification tasks: AUROC and balanced accuracy

Detection tasks: FROC score

Counting and measurement task: Mean Absolute Error

Efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The accuracy metrics are selected based on the recommendation in Metrics Reloaded.

Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods* 21, 195–212 (2024).

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2024 and FLARE 2021-2024.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,

- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will verify the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

TASK 6: Agentic System for Medical Image Analysis

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Agentic systems provide a flexible framework to separate complex tasks into easy-to-solve steps by calling various tools. This task focuses on developing large language model (LLM)-based systems that can interact with users to facilitate and execute diverse medical image analysis tasks. The goal is to design intelligent, conversational agents that serve as intermediaries between medical professionals and sophisticated image analysis tools. These agents should be capable of understanding natural language queries, interpreting user intent, and dynamically invoking relevant medical image analysis algorithms to address specific diagnostic or research needs. By integrating the capabilities of LLMs with task-specific tools, these systems will not only enhance the usability of medical imaging technologies but also empower clinicians to perform complex analyses without requiring extensive technical expertise.

This task challenges participants to develop systems to handle a wide range of tasks, such as segmentation, classification, detection, counting, measurement, regression, and generation. Participants will be provided with a comprehensive dataset for development and evaluation, including:

- Medical Imaging Data: A multimodal collection of CT, MRI, PET, ultrasound, X-ray, OCT, pathology, microscopy, fundus, and endoscopy modalities to support the development of versatile and robust systems.
- Task-Specific Annotations: Ground truth labels for segmentation, classification, detection, and other tasks to train and validate system performance.
- Simulated User Queries: A set of natural language prompts simulating real-world clinical questions and scenarios, designed to test the systems' ability to interpret and respond effectively.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Agentic Systems, Medical Image Analysis, Large Language Models, Task Orchestration, Clinical AI Solutions

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Adibvafa Fallahpour (University of Toronto, Vector Institute)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2024 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Launch challenge registration and release training and validation data.

15 April 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Release validation dataset and open validation submission.

15 August 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Deadline for the testing submission.

1 September 2025 (12:00 AM EST): Invite top teams to prepare presentations and participate in the MICCAI 2025 Satellite Event.

23/27 September 2025: Announce final results at MICCAI.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains and global data contributors with license permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Intervention follow up, Intervention planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Detection, Localization, Prediction, Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with various diseases, which were curated from 50+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Positron Emission Tomography, ultrasound, X-ray, Optical Coherence Tomography, endoscopy, fundus, and microscopy images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The 2D and 3D image data will be released as compressed Nifti1Image and JPEG formats, respectively. These Nifti files will include an affine matrix and header defining the rotation, origin, and spacing of each image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can call various functions for segmentation, classification, detection, counting, measurement, and regression tasks.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Hardware requirements, Runtime

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

[2] Heller N, et al. The kits19 challenge data: 300 kidney tumor cases with clinical context, ct semantic segmentations, and surgical outcomes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00445 (2019).

[3] Clark K, et al. The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): maintaining and operating a public information repository. Journal of Digital Imaging 26, no. 6 (2013)

[4] Ma J, et al. Abdomenct-1k: Is abdominal organ segmentation a solved problem. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (2021).

[5] Grossberg A, et al. Imaging and Clinical Data Archive for Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma Patients Treated with Radiotherapy. Scientific Data 5:180173 (2018)

[6] Fedorov A, et al. DICOM reencoding of volumetrically annotated Lung Imaging Database Consortium (LIDC) nodules. Medical Physics (2020)

[7] Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. The Lancet Digital Health 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

[8] Ma. J, et al. Automatic organ and pan-cancer segmentation in abdomen ct: the flare 2023 challenge. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2408.12534

[9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services
Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil
Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI
BioPartners, CA
Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA
Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA
Cleveland Clinic
Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA
Hebrew University of Jerusalem
International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan
IRCAD Institute Strasbourg
Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA
Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich
M Health Fairview
M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX
Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN
Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)
National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD
National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD
Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montral
Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen
Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY
Sheba Medical Center
St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ
Tel Aviv University
The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)
University of California, San Francisco, CA
University of Chicago
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC
University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA
University of Sheffield
University of Southern California
Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO
Cancer Center West China Hospital
Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT/MR/PET scan or an ultrasound, X-ray, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), endoscopy, fundus, and microscopy image.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training set: 1000+ question-answer pairs and corresponding images

Validation set: 100 question-answer pairs and corresponding images

Testing set: 3000 question-answer pairs and corresponding images

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission and evaluation.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the testing cases are unseen and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

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b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The disease labels are obtained from radiology reports or pathological examinations. Other detection and counting labels are obtained by manual annotations.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Accuracy metrics:

Segmentation task: DSC and NSD

Classification tasks: AUROC and balanced accuracy

Detection tasks: FROC score

Counting and measurement task: Mean Absolute Error

Efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The accuracy metrics are selected based on the recommendation in Metrics Reloaded.

Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods* 21, 195–212 (2024).

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2024 and FLARE 2021-2024.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,

- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will verify the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A